

SOCIAL SCIENCES

MIGRATION PROCESSES IN ASTANA AND THEIR REGULATION

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Abstract

Migration processes are an integral part of the development of modern society, since these processes determine the dynamics of the demographic, social and economic development of the country. In the context of modern globalization, migration is considered one of the most pressing problems that require a detailed study and comprehensive regulatory work.

The article is devoted to the study of the main directions of regulation of migration processes in Astana, the results of the research and recommendations of the author may be important in the development of an effective strategy for sustainable development of the city and control of migration flows, ensuring the social stability of the population of migrants and accommodation.

Keywords: migration processes, regulation of migration processes, legal regulation, principles of migration regulation, human rights.

Before investigating the patterns, directions and difficulties of migration processes and migration relations in state legal regulation, it is necessary to determine the basic principles of regulating migration processes. The basic rules for regulating migration processes should include general legal principles, as well as rules governing migration relations.

A. Zherebtsov's dissertation focuses on the problem of migration relations. In his concept, he distinguishes between "legal relations in the field of population migration" and "migration-legal relations", and also argues that these two concepts have a different structure. [1]

Legal relations in the field of population migration cover a wide range of relations arising from the territorial movement of people and requiring legal regulation. And the essence of migration relations is to change the administrative and legal status of a migrant during the territorial movement of a person. This includes obtaining administrative and legal status by a migrant before the completion of the migration process, its implementation, as well as changing or revoking the status of a migrant.

A. Savchenko understood the regulation of migration relations as legal means and approaches used to optimize the social, economic and political consequences of the migration sphere of the population for public relations. [2]

When developing and implementing the basic principles of regulating migration processes, it is necessary to take into account, first of all, the human rights to freedom of movement, recognized at the international level. International human rights law documents include such general and universal principles as the human right to freedom of movement, the right to choose one's place of residence, and the right to receive housing.

Such international legal acts have been ratified in Kazakhstan, among them the most important are:

– The Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the UN Charter, adopted in 1948; [3]

– The Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Freedoms, adopted in Europe in 1950; [4]

– The International Convention on the Status of Refugees of 1951; [5]

– The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, adopted in 1966; [6]

– The International Covenant on Civil and Political Human Rights. [7]

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights speaks about the right to freedom of movement, the right to choose one's place of residence. In particular, in the declaration "... the right of free movement and choice of place of residence within each State" and "... the right to leave any country, including one's own country and return to one's own country".

Savchenko drew attention to the fact that when developing the principles of migration regulation, migration processes are a complex phenomenon that is broad and comprehensive. Its *migration regulation system* contains the following rules:

– The principle of security - when developing and implementing migration policy, special attention should be paid to ensuring national security.

– The principle of legality - a migrant must strictly comply with the Constitution and other regulations of the country of immigration, as well as human rights and freedoms enshrined in international treaties.

– The principle of equality is to ensure equal protection of the legitimate rights and interests of all citizens by the State, renouncing any privileges and restrictions related to the duration of residence in the territory.

– The principle of justice is to ensure the protection of the rights and interests of migrants from other countries without prejudice to the interests of the settlement.

– The principle of choice is the interest in attracting in-demand specialists and highly qualified immigrants to the country.

– The principle of reliability and transparency - according to this principle, public authorities must

clearly represent the conditions and conditions of migration, and the migrant, in turn, must openly provide all information about himself required by law.

– Scientific principle - it is necessary not only to summarize the effective experience in the field of migration on the part of public authorities, but also to provide scientific provisions and concepts that will serve as the basis for the implementation of regulations.

Following these principles of regulating migration relations, it is possible to ensure the systematic development of the migration policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the socio-economic development of the country.

Based on the migration principles discussed above, it can be noted that the implementation of the migration policy of each country requires a clear assessment and consideration of the economic, social, political, and demographic conditions of the country at the present time. It is necessary to develop basic guidelines and tools for the implementation of migration policy, taking into account foreign experience and the real capabilities of the state.

The history of migration processes in Astana begins with the transfer of the capital of Kazakhstan to Astana, since then the number of migration flows in the direction of Astana has been growing rapidly. According to statistical data for 1996, 278.7 thousand people lived in Astana. And according to the latest data for 2024, the population of Astana is 1 million 430 thousand people. During this time, the city's population has increased by about 5 times, which indicates the intensity of migration processes.

To analyze the causes and structure of migration processes in Astana, first of all, migrants migrating to the city can be divided into the following groups:

1. The first group of migrants in Astana are *seasonal workers and labor migrants*. Migrants of this group are engaged in the construction of industrial and private residential buildings. The shortage of labor resources in Astana and the high wage rate in comparison with other regions of the country are the reason for the emergence of labor migration flows in the capital. [8]

Seasonal workers can be divided into two groups:

– Migrants arriving in Astana in the autumn-winter period from nearby rural areas, as a rule, from Akmola, North Kazakhstan, Kostanay and Ulytau regions, due to the lack of agricultural work at their place of residence;

– Migrants from the southern regions and CIS countries who come in the summer and return to their country with the onset of the cold season, with low incomes. It may be difficult to control the migration of seasonal migrants, since movements within the country are not taken into account, and due to the permission for visa-free entry from many CIS countries, such work as registration of foreign citizens is not carried out.

2. The second group of migrants are *students who arrived in the city for the purpose of education*. This group consists of young people between the ages of 17 and 25. Migration of students is seasonal, that is, the stay of migrants in the city is determined by the period of study in higher educational institutions. There is often an intense flow of migrants between September and

June, and students return to their cities in the summer months.

Students visiting the city of Astana to study can be divided into three categories:

– Students who immigrate from rural areas located near the capital due to the lack or absence of educational institutions at their place of residence.

– Arrival of citizens located far from the capital. The capital status of Astana, the prestige of the university, the high quality of education and employment opportunities in the future are the main reasons for the immigration of students from other cities.

– Students from far abroad, such as India, Pakistan, come for the purpose of education.

3. *The population who arrived for permanent residence in Astana*. They can also be considered in three categories:

– The first group of migrants arriving for permanent residence includes specialists working in the fields of medicine, education, sports, trade and entertainment, who arrived as a result of receiving a job invitation.

– The second category includes people who arrived in order to improve social security and living standards.

– Migration related to family circumstances belongs to the third category. For example, migration, which takes place in order to create a family, migration of parents, reunification with relatives.

In general, people who have moved for permanent residence are associated with such signs as the presence of an average and high income level, the availability of opportunities to purchase or rent housing in Astana.

4. *Pendulum migration* from areas located near the city of Astana, with daily stay at work or study. From the settlements of Kosshy, Koyandy and Talapker, which belong to the Akmola region, but can be considered an agglomeration of Astana, they prefer to work in Astana because of the high level of income in the city. Most residents of suburban villages are not registered at their place of residence, so it is problematic to talk about the actual population in these settlements.

The reasons for the arrival of migrants in Astana can be linked to the improvement of economic and social conditions. It includes such factors and advantages as a relatively high income level in the capital, the labor market, price stability, social security, security, health care and education. The reputation of a city can also be an important factor in facilitating the arrival of migrants.

Conclusions. The inability to control the flow of migrants may cause residents of the host country to fear job loss, increased crime, language and cultural conflicts. Also, in the absence of a report on the arrival of migrants, additional burdens may be imposed on preschool and school education, health care, and social services such as housing construction. The general uncontrolled migration flows impede the effective planning and preparation of urban infrastructure.

Taking into account the main directions of migration processes in Astana, the following principles of regulation in the city can be distinguished:

1. Keeping records of migrants. The implementation of this measure has a number of significant advantages. In particular, ensuring the security of the country by preventing illegal activities; controlling migration flows helps to prevent competition and potential conflicts related to jobs, resources, housing, etc.

2. Protection of the rights and freedoms of migrants. By regulating migration flows, it is possible to ensure the protection of migrants' rights, non-discrimination, and access to social services.

3. Ensuring the adaptation of migrants to Kazakh society. It is necessary to intensify psychological work on the adaptation of migrants to a new environment. For example, assistance to migrants in finding employment, the development of integration and language courses, the operation of centers for migrants in the country for the purpose of social support.

4. Strengthening international relations. The management and regulation of migration flows through the development of cooperation, the exchange of information and experience, and the achievement of joint solutions to common problems related to migration processes.

5. Attracting highly qualified personnel to Kazakhstan. Ensuring the training of national personnel with the involvement of foreign qualified specialists in specialties that are in short supply in the country.

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